

Conditional Sound Effects Generation with Regularized WGAN

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ABSTRACT

Over recent years generative models utilizing deep neural networks have demonstrated outstanding capacity in synthesizing high-quality and plausible human speech and music. The majority of research in neural audio synthesis (NAS) targets speech or music, whereas general sound effects such as environmental sounds or Foley sounds have received less attention. In this work, we study the generative performance of NAS models for sound effects with a conditional Wasserstein GAN (WGAN) model. We train our models conditioned on different classes of sound effects and report on their performances in terms of quality and diversity. Many existing GAN models use magnitude spectrograms which require audio reconstruction using phase estimation after training. The often imperfect reconstruction of the audio signal has led us to propose an additional audio reconstruction loss term for the generator. We show that this additional loss term improves the quality of the audio generation considerably with small sacrifice to the diversity. The results indicate that a conditional WGAN model trained on log-magnitude spectrograms paired with an appropriately weighted reconstruction loss is capable of synthesizing highly plausible sound effects.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sound effects refer to general sounds different from speech or music [1] that often play an important role in digital media or entertainment such as films or video games by enhancing the immersive experience [2]. In most cases they are created from recorded sounds or synthesis engines [3]. A sound designer would then utilize established sound libraries to search for the most appropriate effects that best suit the scenes they are working on. Often, e.g., in a particular game setting, the set of sound categories that is required is small, while the variation within the set of sound categories is important. The number of variations of a given sound type within a sound library is often limited. Using the same audio sample repetitively, e.g. in a game setting, often deteriorates the quality of the perceptual experience. Therefore it is desirable to have many variations of a particular sound type for developing scenes and actions [4, 5]. This happens to be an area of strength for

generative models as they are capable of generating high-quality and diverse sounds that are conditioned on different classes [6, 7]. It is even more so in the domain of Foley sounds for moving images, where previous research [8–11] have explored sound generation by conditioning on visual signals.

In neural audio synthesis, there are two main approaches for modelling sound: modelling the raw waveforms directly [12–15] or modelling the extracted time-frequency (TF) representations [6, 16]. Since audio waveforms can almost completely describe the sounds, it is intuitive to model audio signals directly. Barahona-Ríos and Collins [13] and Marco et al. [14] have explored using conditional WaveGAN and HifiGAN to generate short knocking sounds and footsteps, showing promising results on capturing the fine acoustic details of various kinds given a small and refined dataset. However, both of these research works have only trained on a particular type of sound, namely, impacts comprising single impulses in the waveform. Exactly how well different classes of sounds could be modeled with a conditional waveform-based GAN remains to be explored in detail.

On the other hand, TF representations such as magnitude spectrograms or mel-spectrograms offer many benefits as they provide visual representations that are arguably more interpretable by humans or machines. They are also able to capture and generate some long-range representations utilizing the power of convolutional neural networks (CNN). Often the time and frequency axes are organised to produce square images using short-time Fourier transforms (STFTs). The TifGAN [16] model employs log-magnitude spectrograms with a non-iterative phase estimation algorithm PGHI (Phase Gradient Heap Integration) [17] and achieves high quality sound reconstruction results. Gupta et al. [18] have further explored the generation performance of a progressive GAN model using audio textures such as noise bursts and chirps. They have intriguingly found that the result of using the PGHI method to reconstruct the phase from a magnitude spectrogram outperforms models that are trained using a two-channel representation comprising both the magnitude spectrogram and instantaneous frequency (IF) [19]. We and others have observed that since phase information is abandoned when training on magnitude spectrograms, the reconstruction from such representations is not always perfect even with phase estimation algorithms such as PGHI [17]. This has led many to explore using a neural vocoder [20–22] model to pre-

dict the audio waveform from the magnitude spectrogram. Nonetheless, this involves training an additional model which increases computational resources and time.

In this research, we explore the sound synthesis performance of generative adversarial (GAN) networks conditioned on different categories of sound effects. We create a custom high-quality dataset consisting of five different types of common sound effects and apply a Wasserstein GAN (WGAN) model conditioned on these classes. The WGAN models are trained on log-magnitude spectrogram of the sounds and are evaluated based on the synthesis quality and diversity. The primary contribution of this paper is adding a weighted reconstruction loss term for the generator to reduce the reconstruction error from standard phase reconstruction algorithms [17, 23] and thus eliminate the dependency on a neural vocoder. We demonstrate that this approach improves the synthesis quality by overcoming some of the problems associated with waveform reconstruction based on phase estimation. We also show the proposed method achieves a high Mean-Opinion-Score (MOS) similar to the original training sounds.

2. EXPERIMENTATION SETUP

To set up the experiments, we select a baseline GAN model to perform conditional sound generation. We carefully chose five categories of sound effects and then perform the same preprocessing. We then demonstrate our proposed method.

2.1 Baseline Model

We start with a baseline model which is based on a similar architecture as TifGAN [16] (see Figs.1 and 3). The baseline model is trained with Wasserstein GAN loss including gradient norm penalty [24] (see Fig.1). We utilize a conditioning method that takes a one-hot vector indicating one of five different sound classes. We utilize a conditioning method that takes a one-hot vector indicating one of five different sound classes. In this way, the model is able to synthesize any one of five different types of sounds. The model is trained using log-magnitude spectrograms with size (256,128). For the purposes of comparison, all models use the same hyper-parameters as the baseline model (e.g., 100,000 iterations, a batch size of 16, 1e-4 learning rate).

2.2 Dataset

Sounds	Description	Amount
Footstep	Transient impacts	1170
Gunshots	Transients with long decay	600
Rain	Long-sustaining non-pitched textures	1085
Engine	Long-sustaining pitched textures	1170
Birds	Transients with time-varying high pitches	1420

Table 1. Five types of sounds from real-world recordings

Figure 1. The baseline model is shown with Wasserstein loss formulation and gradient norm penalty training scheme.

Compared with speech and music which are usually normative and structured, sound effects are much more diverse and recordings are usually susceptible to background noises. Common sound effects libraries such as Freesound.org¹ or Audioset² can contain many unwanted sounds in a recording and the quality can vary greatly depending on the recording device, environment, and post-processing. Therefore we created our dataset meticulously by selecting high-quality sound effects from commercial libraries including BBC sound effect³, Soundideas⁴ and Boom Library⁵. For each sound category we selected the sounds that capture slightly different sonic characteristics, such as different contact surfaces for a footstep, or different rain environments recorded at different locations. By carefully and purposely selecting sounds with varying timbral characteristics within each class, we increase the within-class sound diversity. For each category of sound, there are roughly one thousand samples. Although this amount of data is much smaller than what is commonly required for most speech synthesis models, we found it sufficient for our experiments. This amount of training data is similar to previous works [13, 14]. For the sake of comparison, we restrict all of the sound samples to be one second of audio, resulting in 16000 samples at a 16 kHz sample rate. Each recording sample contains a single example for the given sound category, e.g. a single shot for footsteps and gunshots, with clean onsets and offsets. The given formulation of the dataset simplifies the evaluation of the diversity of the sound synthesis.

2.3 Data Processing

The input audio data is zero-padded to a length of 16,384 so that the spectrogram image data are created with a shape of (256,128). To extract the spectrogram, we compute the STFT with a Hanning window using the Tensorflow I/O implementation⁶. For the STFT, the size of the FFT is 254, the window size is 256 and the hop length is 64. Similar to [16], we normalize the magnitude of the STFT data

¹ <https://freesound.org/>

² <http://research.google.com/audioset/>

³ <https://sound-effects.bbcrewind.co.uk/>

⁴ <https://www.sound-ideas.com/>

⁵ <https://www.boomlibrary.com/>

⁶ https://www.tensorflow.org/io/api_docs/python/tfio/audio/spectrogram

to fall within a range of (0,1), take the logarithm to clip their log magnitudes below e^{-10} , then we scale the result down by dividing 5 and shift the output range to [-1,1]. During the generation stage, we apply the Griffin Lim algorithm from the Tensorflow I/O library⁷ with the same windowing settings as previously described.

2.4 Improved Audio Reconstruction

Figure 2. Conditional WGAN with custom MSE loss applied.

In order to improve the audio reconstruction process, we borrow an approach used in neural vocoders and add an additional loss term to our generator. Using the same baseline model during training, we now compare the synthesized audio with a random audio sample of the same sound class chosen from the dataset. We use a Mean-Square-Error (MSE) loss function, L_{rec} , calculated as shown below:

$$L_{rec} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (R_i - F_i)^2, \quad (1)$$

where n represents the batch size, R_i is an audio sample of the same category randomly chosen from the dataset, and F_i is the audio waveform reconstructed from the magnitude spectrum produced by the generator (we use the Tensorflow I/O spectrogram inversion algorithm⁸). We multiply the MSE loss with a hyperparameter weight value, W , to prevent it from overtaking the generator loss. Finally we add the original generator loss L_g such that the final generator loss L_{gen} becomes:

$$L_{gen} = L_{rec} * W + L_g \quad (2)$$

It is worth emphasizing that L_g calculates the loss based on the generated spectrograms, while L_{rec} computes the loss according to the reconstructed audio. The goal of adding the reconstruction loss to the generator is to encourage the generator to synthesize TF representations whose inverted waveforms are similar to the training data. Previous research indicates that adding a reconstruction loss term to GANs reduces diversity [25]. In order to mitigate this side effect, we apply a small scaling factor as a weighting parameter to the loss, $W = 1e^{-4}$. While it is common to train the discriminator using more steps than the generator,

⁷ https://www.tensorflow.org/io/api_docs/python/tfio/audio/inverse_spectrogram

⁸ https://www.tensorflow.org/io/api_docs/python/tfio/audio/inverse_spectrogram

we found instead that training the generator more times than the discriminator gave improved results⁹.

3. EVALUATION

Evaluating audio generation can be a difficult task because there is no ground truth waveform to compare with. Additionally, since hearing perception is subjective, the same waveforms might be perceived differently among different participants. Therefore, we resort to both objective metrics as well as human listening tests to evaluate the synthesis quality/realness and diversity. For evaluation, we decided to generate 1000 samples, a similar amount to our dataset for each category of sound.

3.1 Frechet Audio Distance

The Frechet Audio Distance (FAD) [26] is a reference-free evaluation metric for generated audio quality that measures the similarity between two audio signals by comparing their feature representations through an embedding layer of a pre-trained VGGish model. It has been quite popular over recent years in the neural audio synthesis field and has been used in research such as DarkGAN [27] and Diffwave [28]. Many studies have shown that this metric correlates well with human listeners' preferences [14] and is robust to many audio sources [18, 19]. The smaller the FAD score, the smaller the distance between the original audio and the generated audio and the better the performance of the generative model.

3.2 Number of Statistically Different Bins

Number of Statistically Different Bins (NDB) [29] is an algorithm that has been proposed to evaluate the diversity of generative models [6] and to provide guidance on whether a mode collapse has occurred. It applies K-means clustering of the training data into K-different 'bins' or diversity modes with Voronoi decomposition and then assigns each training and generated data to the closest bin based on an L2 distance. The NDB score is then calculated as the number of bins in a histogram that are considered to be significantly different from each other based on a two-sample binomial test between the training dataset and generated dataset. Since audio waveforms do not usually reveal too much timbral information, we compute the NDB score based on the spectrogram images of the training and generated audio, similar to the approach by Liu et al. [6]. We use 20 K-means bins for each sound class. The choice of number of bins per class is actually dependent on the variations of the datasets. However in our case 20 bins should be sufficient for each single category, as they contain similar waveforms without too much variations. This setting is the same as Liu et al. [6].

3.3 Human Listening Tests

We appreciate that objective metrics alone are not sufficient for neural audio synthesis tasks [30] as the quality

⁹ Our implementation is available online at <https://github.com/Reinliu/CWGAN-SFX>

or realness of a sound is usually dependent on the human listeners' hearing and preference. Therefore, we report a Mean-Opinion-Score (MOS) obtained from eight participant listeners. The participants consist of 5 females and 3 males with ages ranging from 26 to 50 with no previous background in ear training. Each participant was presented with the same pair of headphones and was asked to rate their preference for realness/quality for five types of sounds. There were four experiment conditions for each of the five classes of sound according to whether the audio was selected from either: the training audio from the dataset, the sounds generated from the baseline model, the sounds generated from the new model with the additional loss term, and sounds generated from a WaveGAN used as a control condition. For each sound class(footsteps,rain,etc), we randomly chose four clips of one-second sounds from the four sources mentioned above. Therefore in total, there were 80 sounds that a listener needs to rate on. For each listening test, the listener was presented one sound at a time and was told the category of the sound being played, but was asked to report their preference based on how realistic they perceived the sound to be (e.g., whether it appears be a real/natural audio source or a synthetic audio source). A preference scale from one to five was used: 1 (bad/synthetic) to 5 (excellent/natural). The example sounds could be accessed at ¹⁰.

4. RESULTS

Following our evaluation methods, we show the corresponding results in terms of generation quality and diversity. The results were reported as FAD, MOS, and NDB scores.

4.1 Generation Quality

4.1.1 Frechet Audio Distance(FAD)

Model	Footstep	Bird	Guns	Rain	Engine	Mean
Baseline	2.14	19.43	4.65	10.30	13.84	10.07
Proposed Method	2.07	2.41	5.05	2.64	12.21	4.88
WaveGAN	20.27	33.17	6.22	11.27	27.48	19.68

Table 2. FAD results (Lower means better)

The FAD scores are shown in Table 2. When considering the results across sound categories, please keep in mind that a single conditional WGAN produces all five classes of sound. We observe an overall improvement in audio quality using the proposed method. With the bird and rain sound classes, we see large improvement. Our interpretation for this finding is that these two classes of sounds are arguably more complicated than the other categories. The bird samples consist of several different species of birds chirping and the rain dataset contains recordings from many different environments. Large variations within a particular sound class likely make the job of the generator more difficult. The reconstruction loss likely assists with regularizing across these larger variations. We also observe that

¹⁰ <https://github.com/Reinliu/CWGAN-SFX/tree/main/Sound>

the conditional WaveGAN performs comparatively worse across all sound categories. We interpret this result as indicating that conditioning on different sound categories, rather than variations within a given sound class, was somehow more difficult for the WaveGAN which is based solely on the audio waveform.

4.1.2 Mean Opinion Score(MOS)

Model	Footstep	Bird	Guns	Rain	Engine	Mean
Original	4.5625	4.2188	4.2813	4.1875	4.5938	4.3688
Baseline	3.9375	3.4688	3.9715	3.4375	4.1563	3.775
Proposed Method	4.2188	3.9063	4.1563	4.0313	4.4688	4.1563
WaveGAN	3.6563	2.75	3.5625	2.7188	2.9063	3.1188

Table 3. MOS results (Higher means better)

The Mean-Opinion-Score (MOS) results are shown in Table 3 and 6. The MOS values provide a subjective rating of the plausibility of the sounds. The results indicate that the listening test results correspond well with the FAD results. For the bird and rain sound classes, we again observe relatively larger improvements with the proposed method. The results similarly indicate that the WaveGAN performs worse than the spectrogram-based methods, with an average of 3.1188, 3.775 and 4.1563, respectively, for the WaveGAN, baseline, and proposed methods. It is worth noting that the proposed method achieves a mean score that is similar to the samples from the audio dataset (labelled Original in the table).

4.2 Generation Diversity

4.2.1 Number of Statistically Different Bins(NDB)

Model	Footstep	Bird	Guns	Rain	Engine	Mean
Baseline	0.1	0.25	0.1	0.15	0.2	0.16
Proposed method	0.05	0.3	0.15	0.15	0.25	0.18
WaveGAN	0.1	0.35	0.15	0.2	0.2	0.2

Table 4. NDB/k results are shown for each sound class (lower is better).

Model	Results
Baseline	0.09
Our method	0.10
WaveGAN	0.13

Table 5. NDB/k results are shown for all sound classes combined (lower is better).

The results for the objective diversity measure are shown in Tables 4 and 5. The mean NDB per cluster results are shown for each sound class in Table 4 and the summary results for each synthesis method are shown in Table 5. The results indicate that the baseline network better captures the diversity of the training dataset than the proposed method for all sound classes, except the footsteps sound

class. This is generally to be expected because of the additional loss term in the generator. We cannot explain the exception for the footstep class. The relative reduction in diversity seems a reasonable trade-off for the improvement in quality. The future work could be improving the diversity by modifying the MSE loss term. At the moment we are regularizing the mean of our generated audio in a batch to be similar to randomly chosen real audio in a same amount of batch. However this does not guarantee that the audio from each bin could be selected equally throughout the training. In future works, we could force audio from each bin to be selected in equal amount so that the model learns to capture all the variations throughout training. We think this would improve the diversity score.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this research we have studied the performance of NAS models for five classes of sound effects. We show that for this particular type of conditional generation across different sound classes, the WGAN model trained on log-magnitude spectrograms achieves better performance than the WaveGAN model. We proposed a regularization method based on the waveform reconstruction error to help improve the performance of the GAN's generator. The performance results indicate that there is value in this approach with regards to achieving substantial improvement in audio quality, while suffering a small loss in diversity.

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